

TECHNOLOGY OF PREPARING CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article provides information about the speech deficits of children with autism, the importance of inclusive education and methods of preparing them for school education. Scientists who have conducted research on the speech deficits of children with autism spectrum and information about the main problems that prevent them from studying in an inclusive class in a general education school are presented.

Key words: children with autism spectrum disorder, inclusive education, Bleuler, the main problems that prevent children with autism spectrum disorders from studying in an inclusive classroom in a general education school.

The main problems that prevent children with autism spectrum disorder from studying in an inclusive class in a general education school:

- ✓ ☐ clear unevenness and uniqueness of the development of mental functions;
- ✓ uniqueness and insufficient development of general cognitive activity;
- ✓ difficulties in establishing effective relationships with other people;

Currently, as the possibility of having children with disabilities is prevented, according to statistics, we can see that the number of children diagnosed with early childhood autism is constantly increasing every year. In 1997-2017, the number of patients with such a diagnosis increased 10 times, and in 2020 it was shown that pregnancy and childbirth, and complications can increase the probability of the occurrence of this disease only in the presence of other causative factors. The main thing is that the real causes of this disease have not been fully determined.

Autism is a complex developmental disorder that includes problems with social interaction, language acquisition, and a range of emotional, cognitive, motor, and sensory skills, as well as delays in the development of these skills, along with behavioral abnormalities. specific forms are observed.

The concept of "autism" was first introduced in 1911 by E. Bleuler. The author stated that autism is a separation from reality based on affective complexes and thought disorders characteristic of schizophrenia and other pathological conditions.

In individuals with autism:

- ✓ ☐ biological basis of autism is structural disorders in brain development;
- ✓ development of memory, attention, verbal thinking, communication, etc.;
- ✓ we can see the presence of functional disorders of the brain.

It has been reported that several studies show that the genetic characteristics of a person with autism are also identified, and geneticists have not yet been able to identify the genes responsible for the development of this disease. The medical anamnesis of autistic

children revealed that expectant mothers experienced autistic complications during pregnancy.

Autism is a serious socio-psychological and pedagogical problem. Currently, we can see that the development of special technologies of education and training of children with autism spectrum in school education based on inclusive education is a problem. In preparing children with autism spectrum for school education, it directs the development of pronunciation skills, listening attention, verbal (speech) memory, articulatory motor skills. Below are examples of how to pronounce sounds correctly, to recognize their expression in writing, and to teach the places where these sounds are used in words:

1. Determining the position of the sound "A" in words such as "bear", "watermelon", "apple" depicted in the pictures.
2. Remember the words with the sound "A" and identify them.
3. Making letters with fingers.
4. Creating letters from pencils, wooden sticks or cuttings.

In conclusion, I can say that we can see that the use of instructional materials, audio sounds and new pedagogical technologies in preparing children with autism spectrum for school education leads to effective results. To teach children the ability to pay attention to the emotional state of other people, to recognize emotions, to respond appropriately to them, to analyze their emotions. Technologies aimed at the development of the social sphere of children with autism include positive self-evaluation, self-management, independence, development of moral qualities, mastering humane ways of interacting with people, basic behavioral ethics technologies of teaching and speech development: development of the skills of correct pronunciation of sounds, phonemic hearing, sound analysis of words, development of dialogic and monological speech, lexical and grammatical categories.

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